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A note on preservation of language in ancient time

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In the age of present day, preservation of languages can be viewed through the efforts of the government policies and the effective use of technology. The language preservation has two aspects. To encourage its use in more and more domains is one aspect. Putting emphasis on purity, eliminating influence of other languages is another aspect of preserving the same. The new generation could be encouraged to learn the language which is to be preserved through the educational policies, thus, handing over it to the next generation. World wide efforts are made to preserve the spoken form of the endangered languages through audiotapes, videotapes, and apps and other machine tools. Sanskrit is one of the oldest preserved languages of the world. In the Indian subcontinent, it is handed down from centuries together till today in oral and written forms. In ancient period, when several forms of the language were in use, one of the varieties was codified by the rules of grammar which later on came to be known as Sanskrit. The texts composed in Sanskrit are handed down from generation to generation in oral and written tradition. Sanskrit is an exemplifier of successful language preservation through ages.

The present paper tries to reflect on the motive behind this preservation and various strategies adopted for preservation in the ancient time.

This language was not only considered as a means of communication but other religious and spiritual values were also attached to it. The language was considered to be of divine origin. RV 8.100.11 says “the gods created this divine speech which is spoken in by various beings. Let that cow, who is well-praised bestowing vigour and strength approach us” (translated). It was considered as a means of praising Gods. The prime importance was given to the perfect utterance of speech without even a smallest variation in a letter, accent or length.

It was believed that a Mantra uttered accurately will only convey the intended meaning and not the other one. The wrongly uttered Mantra was considered to bring evil on the reciter. Further, it was believed that utterance of a single correct word will lead to heaven. The purpose behind attaching religious and spiritual merits to the correct utterance and study of language through grammar appears to be in accordance with people’s belief in religion and spirituality, where they thought that good deeds lead to merits. And the study of language no longer remained a worldly affair.

It was believed that the Vedas, the sacred texts would be preserved only through the preservation of language. The preservation strategies pertain to all levels of languages such as phonetic, morphemic, syntactic and textual. The Siksas and Pratisakhayas are the

treatises which form a part of Vedangas, ancillary texts for the study and preservation of the Vedas. The Siksas deal with the speech sounds. They describe the places and manners of articulation of all the sounds. They are rightly described in the Paniniyasiksa as Manual of pronunciation. They describe the pulmonic air steam mechanism, phonation, nasalization, aspiration, state of glottis, length of vowels and so on. To record the accuracy of pronunciation, Paniniyasiksa gave analogies of bird and animal sounds which were familiar to common people. Further, the Pratisakhyas texts deal with the minute details of pronunciation in a particular recension of Vedas. Speech sound is the smallest or atomic unit of language. It is dealt very scientifically by Siksas and Pratisakhyas.

The Nighantu is a lexical work which collects lists of the Vedic words. It is the foremost lexicon or dictionary that arranges synonyms belonging to different categories. The words gone out of use were difficult to comprehend at a later period. Therefore, Nighantu made an attempt to collect such words which were falling in disuse in his times. The Nighantu systematically collected and analyzed the words according to their meanings. The principles of Lexicography such as lemmatization, meaning-wise arrangement etc. could be traced in Nighantu. The Nirukta attempts at the etymologies of the words preserved in Nighantu. It tries to derive the words from verbal roots. This facilitated to reveal the meanings and thereby preservation of those words.

The Siksas and Pratisakhyas were successful in preservation of language on phonetic and phonological level. While the Nighantu and Nirukta preserved the language on lexical level. They created good background for grammatical study of language. The grammar, Vyakarana refers to analysis of the word. It is a means to describe the language by analyzing it into its components.

The Astadhyayi of Panini is intended for the entire study of language on all levels phonological, morphological and syntactic. Panini devised several rules to describe different phenomena of language by setting general rules and exceptions. It presented good model for language preservation. The followers of Panini noted the changes from time to time. But in principle they adhered to the rules set by Panini. Thus, the language became codified with Panini's grammatical system so much so that in later

centuries whatever was not 'Prescribed' by Panini was rendered to be 'wrong' using the word.

The Siksas and Pratisakhyas being Vedangas were primarily for the preservation of Vedas but the phonetic description provided by them is comprehensive and is applicable to Vedic and non-Vedic forms of the language. Similarly, Panini's Astadhyayi is also the grammar of both Vedic and non-Vedic words.

We would like to draw the attention to preservation of sacred Vedic texts. The Padapatha by Saunaka divided the continuous utterance of Rgvedasamahita into words or Padas, thus preserving each and every word in isolation removing euphonic combinations in its original accent. The Padapata also provides analysis of compound words by way of insertion of Avagraha. It is a systematic division of sentence into constituent words. The Krama reading is a peculiar 'step by step' arrangement of a Vedic text by combining the Samhitapata and the Padapata by giving the words both as connected and unconnected with following and preceding words to eliminate all possible errors. Eight Vedic Vikrtis, the recitation modes are further attempts to preserve the language on textual level. These are Sikha, Mala, Jata, Rekha, Dhvaja, Danda, Ratha, and Ghana.

In the absence of any formal or official agency as such, the above-mentioned treatises prove to be the conscious efforts towards language preservation in the ancient time. The success of these preservation strategies lies in the fact that for the span of more than 2 millennia, this form of language is seen without much variation throughout all the genres of literature such as the epics, Puranas, Sastric texts, poems and plays and so on composed in different parts of India.